

FINE AND APPLIED ARTS ABOUT THE PERIODS OF DEVELOPMENT OF POTTERY

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Abstract: This article discusses the modern and ancient periods of pottery, the history of the art of pottery, its emergence, and the stages of development. It also discusses the practical and creative work being carried out to develop pottery today.

Kalit so'zlar: Kulolchilik, sopol, bezak, loy, neolit davri, badiiy bezatish usullari, kulolchilik maktablari, kulol, charx, angob.

Abstract: This article examines the modern and ancient periods of pottery, the history of pottery, its formation, and the stages of its development. It also discusses the practical and creative work being done today to advance the art of pottery.

Key words: ceramics, pottery, ornament, clay, Neolithic, artistic design methods, pottery schools, fired stone, engobe.

Abstract: This article examines the modern and ancient pottery periods, the history of pottery, its formation, and the stages of development. We are talking about the practical and creative work that is being carried out today on the development of pottery.

Keywords: ceramics, ornament, clay, Neolithic, methods of decoration, pottery schools, baked stone, angob.

In Uzbekistan, a lot of work is being carried out at the level of our Republic to develop and promote applied arts. This is also reflected in the draft resolutions signed by our President on the work being carried out. In particular, the Cabinet of Ministers adopted Resolution No. 1003 dated 20.12.2017 "On the establishment of the State Museum of the History of Applied Arts and Crafts of Uzbekistan" on the development of applied arts. It was established on the basis of the Museum of Applied Arts of Uzbekistan in Tashkent.

The main areas of the museum's activities are:

- to preserve, widely promote internationally, scientifically study and pass on to future generations the traditions of unique schools of applied arts and national crafts, as well as works of applied arts and crafts that have survived to this day;

- truthfully covering the history and rich cultural heritage of our people's applied arts and national crafts, as well as its role in the history of humanity;

- organisation of museum expositions aimed at widely promoting the achievements of our country in culture, art and other areas;
- to preserve, study, enrich, exhibit, introduce and promote to the world community museum objects and museum collections, which are considered the cultural wealth of our people;
- To educate and strengthen the sense of respect, pride and honour for national and universal human values among citizens, especially the younger generation, through the display of unique exhibits;
- to carry out scientific research on museum objects and museum collections and to publish their results. [1]

The museum also has a collection of works by a number of masters in the field of applied art, including pottery. Today, museums of applied art operate in the Andijan region, as in all regions of our republic.

In accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 975 dated December 11, 2017, on approving the Program of Measures for Further Improvement and Development of the Activities of State Museums in 2017-2027, the activities of the museums in the existing Asaka, Bulokboshi, Shahrikhan, Ulug'nor, Jalaquduk, Kurgantepa, and Izboskan districts of Andijan region were terminated in 2018, and the exhibits, collections, and material and technical base of all museums in the fund were transferred to the Andijan Regional Museum of History and Culture, which was reorganized in 2017. Today, this museum serves to the best of its ability to provide information on the history of Andijan pottery.

The museum's collection contains a large number of ceramic objects found in the Andijan region. All ceramic objects are divided into periods and presented to museum visitors. Among the exhibits are works of master potters from the 19th-20th centuries, starting from the period before Christ. These exhibits are located in the applied arts department on the second floor of the museum.

In the first collection of glazed exhibits, under number 2, there are the remains of a set of decorative vessels dating back to the 2nd-1st millennia, found in the Jalaquduk district of Andijan region. Under numbers 4 and 5, there are ceramic pots belonging to the same period, under number 6, there is a ceramic tray, and part of a ceramic vase. In the technology of processing ceramic products of these periods, the surface of the ceramic products was decorated with red glaze. It is not difficult to know that the ceramic products were well processed until they had a flat surface. During this period, ceramic products were made symmetrically. As a result of research conducted in this area, many valuable findings were recorded. In addition to these glazed ceramic products, a ceramic

pot and other ceramic products dating back to the 2nd-1st millennia, found in the Jalaquduk district of Andijan region, were included in the collection of later exhibits. The ceramic pot is recorded under serial number 2. Among the rare finds that have been well preserved to this day, there is also a ceramic vase. Narrow-necked jars and ceramic date pots from the collection also provide information about the pottery of this period. The pottery was made using special pottery tools, which were convenient for the period. This indicates that craftsmanship was well developed in Dalvarzintepa during this period.

The museum's collection contains items found in various locations in the Andijan region, which are arranged in a unique way according to the periods and locations where they were found. Among the finds in the Shu'rtepa settlement in the Asaka district of the Andijan region, valuable ceramic items were also found. These items are also included in the museum's collection. It is noteworthy that these ceramic items date back to the 6th-7th centuries. The outer part of the ceramic items is decorated with a special wavy decoration using a special marking tool. The collection includes ceramic items with handles. It is not difficult to understand that they were made by a master potter of the Humga period, with a special tap and handle for liquid. During this period, potters emphasised the convenience of using ceramic items in addition to the elegance of their ceramic items. [3]

Among the pottery items in the museum, a unique collection of ceramic items found in various locations in the Andijan region always attracts all visitors. Among them is a zoomorphic vessel with an animalistic appearance. The ceramic item resembles decorative ceramic items intended for pouring liquids, namely wine. The ceramic item has a narrow neck and a simple handle. On the other side of the ceramic item, the head of the animal is embossed. This collection also includes a jug created using the technique of scratching the ceramic item with a hard object.

The centrepiece of the collection is a ceramic humcha with a complex pattern. There are broken handles on both sides of the humcha. The humcha is decorated with a red engobe pattern, and the narrowing part of the humcha has a horizontal Islamic pattern. The centre of the lower humcha has a narrowing pattern in accordance with the shape of the ceramic object. These two patterns are completed with lines. The inner side of the ceramic object is not decorated. The outer side is polished. It is one of the best-preserved ceramic objects to date, enriching the museum's exhibits. [4]

Another unique feature of the collection is the engraving of special symbols and prayers on the surface of the ceramic objects. Among these ceramic objects, a

jug with an ancient Fergana inscription on the surface of a ceramic object found in Zavroktepa, Andijan district, Andijan region, was found. This ceramic object was found to belong to the 5th-7th centuries. Another jug found in the Andijan region also had a Uyghur inscription scratched on the handle. Researchers noted that this inscription was written in Uyghur script and that it said "Beware of illness and disappointments," as noted by scientists from the Andijan region Museum of History and Culture. Ceramic objects are made of porcelain, faience, and majolica, also known as earthenware and ceramics. The production of ceramic objects first began in Egypt in the 4th millennium BC. The Chinese learned the secrets of making porcelain objects at the beginning of the AD. The word majolica is derived from the Spanish island of Majorca, and the word faience from the Italian city of Faenza. Pottery is a type of craft that produces various objects (terracotta, earthenware, building materials, etc.) from clay. They first made dishes from clay and fired them in a fire. Since clay was available from all over the world, pottery was widespread. The potter's wheel was invented in the early 3rd millennium BC. Simple methods of pottery are still used by people living in the mountainous regions of Asia. Excavated remains of Neolithic settlements show that pots were made with pointed bottoms (pots were sunk into the ground). [5]

Humanity has been engaged in pottery since the Neolithic era. It is the most ancient and youthful art of the East, creating miraculous beauty from special clay. This black clay is a symbol of generosity, honesty, and goodness. Soil is the basis of the highest form of art, prosperity, abundance, sustenance, and beauty, which takes on all human needs. All people of the world are engaged in pottery. Initially, women were engaged in pottery, which ensured the widespread spread of pottery. With the advent of the pottery wheel, men were also involved in this work. The dishes were baked in special ovens and kilns.

During the Eneolithic period, the production of fine pottery and the use of clay in architecture flourished in the countries of the East and Greece. After the discovery of glazing methods, [1]the artistic value of pottery increased. They began to create and reproduce products themselves, not limited to consuming them. Now, in addition to hunting, they also began to engage in animal husbandry and agriculture. The production process intensified, and at the same time, the spiritual world and worldview of people became more complex.

Pottery is the oldest and most youthful art of the East, which creates miraculous beauty from black clay. This black clay is a symbol of generosity, honesty, and goodness. The soil is the basis of the highest form of art, which takes on all the needs of people - prosperity, abundance, sustenance, and beauty. All

people of the world are engaged in pottery. They differ from each other in their own unique aspects.

In the history and development of mankind, pottery first appeared in the Neolithic or New Stone Age, when people began to create and reproduce products not only from nature, but also from clay. They began to make various objects from clay, and decorating them with patterns became widespread. Parallel, spiral and wavy lines, concentric circles formed the basis of many patterns of this period. Since the ancient world, this field has developed significantly not only in the West, but also in the countries of Central Asia. In the study of Central Asian art and culture, examples of pottery have been found in castles, palaces, dwellings and tombs that have survived to our time. [6]

Today, along with all types of art, the attention paid to the activities of pottery schools and artistic masters has increased somewhat. In 1997, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to support the further development of folk crafts and applied arts through state means" became an effective impetus for the development of pottery traditions, along with all other areas.

- In cities, foot-powered wheels have long been used to make pottery.
- From the 9th century onwards, the division of production in workshops to different owners (sculptors, painters, potters);
- The introduction of the use of moulds for mass production of objects from the 9th to the 20th centuries.
- From the 9th to 11th centuries, the surface of spool objects was filled with a composition of whole images;
- In the 9th-10th centuries, beautiful inscriptions were added to the surface of objects;
- Starting from the 9th century, the production of high-quality alkali from natural plants for glazing objects began.
- Increased attention to the functional convenience of objects in the 9th-12th centuries;
- The use of certain spool shapes that have passed the test of time as a template for mass production.
- The use of printed patterns in Movaraunnahr in the 10th-11th centuries.
- The use of pottery in the 12th century in Merv.
- The revival and flourishing of the art of pottery in the 14th-15th centuries.
- The use of tiles in pottery in the 14th century.
- In the 14th century, a pattern was created in bright blue on a white surface;

The mid-19th century saw the development of porcelain-like pottery at the Rishton Pottery School. [7]

References used:

1. D. A. Nozilov O'rta Osiyo dizayni tarixidan Toshkent "O'zbekiston" 1998
2. M. K. Rahimov O'zbekiston badiiy keramikasi Toshkent 1961
3. L. Jadova Современная керамика Узбекистана 1963
4. С. С. Булатов, М. О. Аширова Амалий санъат қисқача луғати 1992
5. М. Sh. Mannonova "O'zbek kulolchilik terminologiyasi" dissertatsiya
6. G.Shatskiy. Koyalardagi kadimgi rasmlar. T.; 1973.
7. . С.Булатов. "Халқ таълими" журнали. Т.; 1998, 1-сон